

Modeling the Tiltrotor Shipboard Flight Test Environment

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Abstract—The shipboard flight test environment can present a hostile scenario to both conventional rotorcraft and tiltrotor aircraft. The aircraft configuration is not typically optimized for the ship airwake turbulence, ship motion, or the confined landing area factors that make shipboard operational requirements unique. Recent tiltrotor control difficulties were encountered during aircraft testing operations aboard an amphibious class ship. It is important to determine the effects of the primary shipboard landing parameters to help support future at-sea testing. Ongoing analytic efforts are required to evaluate the effect of a computational fluid dynamics (CFD) ship airwake model on blade element tiltrotor aircraft models for the shipboard landing task. Air vehicle model tradeoffs required to achieve a real time capability need to be evaluated. This paper reviews the set-up of a tiltrotor blade element model, initial model validation and real time piloted shipboard landing simulation, plus assessment of the analytic model capability to support future rotorcraft/ship.

the rotorcraft shipboard landing task for a specific set of test conditions. The rotorcraft flight control system is usually designed to help optimize land-based flying qualities and structural requirements. This optimization does not usually consider the ship-based airwake and associated turbulence. It is importance to investigate the importance of levels of complexity of rotorcraft and airwake models used to support rotorcraft/ship testing, related analysis, and training.

A need exists to develop an improved analytical capability to support Dynamic Interface (DI) testing. DI testing involves all aspects of rotorcraft/ship compatibility, with emphasis on establishing launch/recovery envelopes. The shipboard operating limits are functions of wind-over-the-deck speed and direction, ship pitch and roll, visual conditions, and pilot workload associated with specific rotorcraft/ship combinations. It is logistically difficult to schedule rotorcraft/ship combinations for testing in high wind and sea state conditions. Testing may be conducted in areas of low ambient winds, and these tests may have to be repeated several times to get large operational envelopes, thus increasing the program time and cost factors. Work has been ongoing for several years to develop an analytical capability, but the capability to develop operational envelopes using simulation does not exist. The importance of the major rotorcraft/ship problem components (rotor and airwake) level of complexity needs to be analyzed in non-real time and in real time pilot in the loop simulation.

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1. BACKGROUND

Navy and Marine Corps rotorcraft are designed to operate from a variety of ship classes, including amphibious class ships and surface combatants. The ship size, shape, and geometry/inertia dictate the ship motion characteristics. The ship topside design dictates the airflow and turbulence characteristic resulting from a specified wind over the deck speed and direction and ship speed. The ship airwake and motion, combined with the aircraft controllability characteristics, dictate pilot effort required when performing

2. ROTORCRAFT/AIRWAKE MODEL

This shipboard landing study focused on the V-22 tiltrotor model. The V-22 first flight occurred in 1989 and since then the aircraft has completed approximately 5000 flight hours. The aircraft was grounded for a couple of years, but is now flying to complete Engineering Manufacturing Development testing. The rotorcraft features two three bladed tilt rotors that can be varied from 96 deg (helicopter mode) to zero deg (airplane mode). The aircraft features a triple redundant digital flight control system that includes an automatic flight control system (AFCS) and a primary flight control system (PFCS). The PFCS provides basic aircraft control, thrust/power management, force feel, and trim

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control. The AFCS provides full time rate stabilization and selectable attitude stabilization and flight director system.

Analytic Models—The V-22 development program is supported by several analytic programs at Bell/Boeing and other activities, but real time pilot-in-the-loop support is provided by an enhanced Generic Tilt Rotor Simulation (GTRSIM) Model. This model is based on an early 1970's Bell and NASA Generic Tilt Rotor simulation. GTRSIM uses a rotor disk aerodynamics model that has been extensively modified to reflect changes to the V-22 prototype rotorcraft, and flight test data collected. The rotor disk model features uniform induced velocity across the entire disk.

The V-22 blade element model is the V-22 MFS model converted to the Flightlab environment by related small business innovative research programs and NAVAIR science and technology programs. The Flightlab model includes blade element rotor model with flight control system and aircraft aerodynamic interference components from the MFS GTRSIM model. Figure 1 shows the Xanalysis applications of Flightlab that includes both flying qualities and performance and Dynamic Interface test support. The low speed air vehicle flying qualities and performance screen is presented as figure 2. Figure 3 shows the Dynamic Interface test support page. The stationkeeping or hovering over the ship option is shown in figure 4. The Flightlab blade element V-22 model can be used for both real time pilot-in-the-loop test support and non-real time analysis. The Flightlab V-22 model validation focused on the low speed flight regime, as might be experienced in the shipboard landing scenario. The Flightlab air vehicle model was also integrated with different ship airwake models to support the shipboard landing task.

Ship Airwake Models—Both time-varying and steady airwake with superimposed turbulence models were used. The NAVAIR 4.3.2.1 Advanced Aerodynamics Group generated the CFD time varying airwake data. The CFD ship airwake data were generated using the COBALT code that solves the Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes equations. The MILES turbulence model was used to simulate the boundary layer. CFD airwake data were generated for the complete LHA ship flowfield in 15 deg increments, and the grid density over the ship landing areas were 5 ft, as shown in figure 5.

The CFD steady plus turbulence airwake data approach involves deriving steady and root mean square components from the time varying airwake data to obtain a more computational efficient solution. The turbulence model is based on processing white noise inputs with shaping filters to produce RMS values that are stored as a function of position in space. Both off-line and real time tests can be run to compare the results of both the time varying and frequency domain CFD airwake solutions.

3. MODEL CONFIGURATION

Rotorcraft Model Validation—The Flightlab V-22 blade element model was compared to the MFS GTRSIM model in the low speed flight regime. Model data in the form of response to control step and doublet inputs were compared. Data were obtained for automatic control system ON and OFF at hover and at 40 kt. Figures 6 and 7 show the comparison of control input, angular acceleration, angular rate, and attitude for a lateral control doublet in hover, with the automatic flight control system on. The time response of the two models shows a very close comparison. Figure 8 shows a comparison for left directional step input. The angular acceleration, rate, and attitude show good correlation, although the maximum yaw angular acceleration of the two models are slightly displaced. Figures 9 and 10 show a comparison of the two models at 40 kt forward speed. These figures show a very good correlation between the responses to a lateral cyclic doublet. Additional comparisons between the blade element model and the actual V-22 aircraft will be performed in the future as soon as aircraft test data becomes available.

Aircraft/Airwake Model Integration—The Flightlab V-22 blade element model featured five segments per blade that calculated the forces and airloads associated with that blade segment. The Flightlab model also includes an LHA ship model. The CFD grid structure and the Flightlab ship model used a different coordinate system and velocity component system, requiring a transformation. The ship airwake data were generated for each CFD grid point. The Flightlab program normalizes the ship airwake velocity outputs using wind over the deck magnitude. Ship airwake velocities can be obtained from each x, y, and z location around the ship.

Simulation Set-up Configuration—The real time pilot-in-the-loop demonstration was conducted at the NAVAIR Manned Flight Simulator (MFS). The MFS features a six degree of freedom motion base system, visual systems, replaceable cockpits, and the control hardware. The control and simulation test loop evaluation (CASTLE) software is used to tie the hardware components together and serve as the host for simulation models. The motion platform is designed to provide pitch, roll, yaw angular response, plus vertical, lateral, and longitudinal linear response in any combination with a maximum of ± 0.8 g in the vertical axis and ± 0.7 g in both longitudinal and lateral axes. The visual hardware is provided by a Rediffusion WIDE display system consisting of 5 collimated channels that provide a 40 deg vertical by 200 deg horizontal field-of-view. The visual scene is provided by a SK1 system. The baseline MFS V-22 airframe model includes the aerodynamics, rotor, and engine modules and runs at 60Hz.

The Flightlab simulation model was implemented at the MFS on a 2.2 GHz dual-processor, Linux-based personal computer that could run the V-22 blade element model and CFD ship airwake model in real time. The Flightlab model was connected the SGI CASTLE interface via an Ethernet.

Shared memory is used to connect the CASTLE shell structure to the visual system, the stick loader, and the V-22 cockpit.

Integration Timing Options—Following the Flightlab and CASTLE integration in the MFS, the difference in each program cycle time and the manner in which data were transferred resulted in visual scene jitter, especially noticeable when the aircraft was maneuvered near the ship. Following several adjustments, the visual scene appeared smoother, but additional work is needed to completely resolve this problem. The pilots also noted a lag between the cockpit stick (especially longitudinal) and the resulting visual scene response. An upcoming program is scheduled to document all time delay associated with the V-22 model at the MFS.

4. PILOTED OPTIONS

Flight Profile—One goal was to make the simulation flight profile as realistic as possible, and at the same time, minimize the flight time for each simulation run. Starting the simulation run at the 180 degree position of the downwind portion of a standard shipboard landing approach would give the pilot a chance to get stabilized before entering the final approach. This approach profile is summarized in figure 11.

Pilot Comments—General qualitative comments were obtained from two test pilots. Pilot A was a Bell/Boeing test pilot with over 5000 flight hours, including over 350 flight hours in the V-22, plus a Marine Corps background. Pilot B was a Marine Corps V-22 pilot with over 3000 flight hours, including approximately 50 flight hours in the V-22. Each pilot had one flight, and comments were solicited on the blade element model compared to the baseline GTRSIM model and the effect of landing on different spots and the effects of the airwake models.

The pilot comments were basically positive. Pilot A noted that the Flightlab model compared well with the GTRSIM baseline model. He noted a lag between control input, especially longitudinal, and the visual system response. (Time delays are currently being investigated.) He also noted a tendency for lateral oscillations when landing on LHA spot 7 with winds from 030 degrees. Pilot B noted a tendency to get "sucked toward the ship" when making an approach within 100-200 ft from the ship.

5. FUTURE PLANS

This work was accomplished at the end of the fiscal year and additional work is required to validate the blade element model compared to actual aircraft test data for low speed test conditions. More work also is required to optimize the synchronization between the PC-based Flightlab model and the CASTLE shell structure at the MFS. Future plans also

include a comprehensive piloted evaluation of aircraft and airwake sensitivity parameters.

6. SUMMARY

The feasibility of using a blade element rotorcraft model and a CFD airwake model to study the effect of level of model complexity on the shipboard landing task was demonstrated. A Flightlab blade element V-22 model was setup at the NAVAIR MFS and integrated the MFS CASTLE shell structure. Differences in model cycle time and data transfer rate resulted in visual scene jitter. Following timing and synchronization adjustments the scene jitter was minimized and limited pilot qualitative comments were collected. Limited quantitative data were also obtained and is currently being analyzed.

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Dean Carico is a senior aerospace engineer in the rotorcraft shipboard suitability group in test and evaluation engineering at the Naval Air Systems Command at Patuxent River, MD. He has over 35 years experience working on Navy and Army flight test and related analytic/simulations programs. Dean was the lead engineer in the Navy's first

rotorcraft operational flight trainer (OFT) evaluation for SH-2F Device 2F106. As the Rotary Wing Aircraft Test Directorate Simulation Specialist during the late eighties, Dean was lead engineer in a multi-year program on Rotorcraft Simulation to Support Flight Testing. As the first Dynamic Interface Section Head, Dean initiated a combined flight test and analytic program in 1983. Dean is currently lead in an internal science and technology program that focused on determining the effect of math model complexity in analyzing the rotorcraft shipboard landing task. Dean also initiated a high performance computing program on flight test automation, and over fifteen small business

innovative research programs that focus on enhancing rotorcraft land and ship-based flight testing. He developed a Joint Test & Evaluation program concept in 1997 that could be used to greatly enhance conventional T&E. Dean has masters' degrees in Aerospace Engineering from Princeton and in Engineering Science from the Navy Postgraduate School, and is an engineering graduate from the USNTPS. He received the Meritorious Civilian Service Award for testing in a combat zone in 1973, and the Richard L. Wernecke Award for technical excellence in rotorcraft test and evaluation in 1997.

Figure 1 – Flightlab Xanalysis Applications

ID	Test Type	Test Conditions				Test Configuration			FCS	Others	Plot
		AS	Hp	OAT	Hr	WT	FSCG	BLCG			
		KCAS	FT	Deg C	RPM	LBS	Inch	Inch	1/0		
#1	Hover	0	0	15	257.6	16300	360	0	1	Inputs...	Results...
#2	Critical Airspeed	20	0	15	257.6	16300	360	0	1	Inputs...	Results...
#3	Low Speed	0	0	15	257.6	16300	360	0	1	Inputs...	Results...
#4	Level Flight	40	0	15	257.6	16300	360	0	1	Inputs...	Results...
#5	Forward Climb	60	0	15	257.6	16300	360	0	1	Inputs...	Results...
#6	Lrg Stat Stability	60	0	15	257.6	16300	360	0	1	Inputs...	Results...
#7	Lst Stat Stability	60	0	15	257.6	16300	360	0	1	Inputs...	Results...
#8	Lrg Dyn Stability	60	0	15	257.6	16300	360	0	1	Inputs...	Results...
#9	Coordinated Turn	60	0	15	257.6	16300	360	0	1	Inputs...	Results...
#10	Autoreotation	60	0	15	257.6	16300	360	0	1	Inputs...	Results...

Figure 2 – Flightlab Performance & Stability Matrix

Figure 3 – Dynamic Interface Test Page

Figure 4 – DI Stationkeeping Analytic Options

Figure 5A – LHA CFD Grid Top View

Figure 5B – LHA CFD Grid Front View

Figure 5C - CFD WOD Conditions Generated for LHA Class Ship

Figure 6 – Left Hover Doublet

Figure 7 – Right Hover Doublet

Figure 8 – Pedal Step Hover

Figure 9 – Lt Lateral Doublet 40 kts

Figure 10 – Rt Lateral Doublet 40 kts

Figure 11 - Rotorcraft/Ship Simulation Landing Pattern